

TENSILE AND FRACTOGRAPHIC EVALUATION WITH VARYING TEMPERATURE AND MOISTURE CONTENT OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The advent of the composite materials and the knowledge acquired in the recent years in this area has increased the performance of the aeronautical industries' products. Carbon fibres reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites have the environmental friendly advantage over the thermosetting composites that can be processed many times and can be recycled. However, one disadvantage of the CFRTP is the restrict knowledge in how this material behaves when in aggressive environment, such as under low temperatures (below 0°C) and after an absorption of certain percentage of moisture. Tests were conducted at different temperatures: (+20°C), (+0°C), and (-55°C), under various percentages of moisture-absorbed contents. Fractographic analyses were made to help in the understanding of the failure mode. Results shown that differences in the rupture strength at the conditions tested were not big. Changes in moisture content, for a constant temperature, have almost no effect on the rupture strength value. However, increasing temperature, for the same moisture content, the rupture strength shows a little tendency to decrease.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic Composites, Low Temperatures, Moisture Content, Tensile Test, Fractographic Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Fractography

Fractography is one of the most used techniques in failure analysis of damaged components/materials. It consists of making the identification of fractographic aspects and than to make a connection between the presence or not of those features with the fracture events sequence. This can lead to the determination of the failure causes and conditions that caused the component/material to fail. The main help given by Fractography is to confirm or not suspects about the failure mode [1, 2].

To make Fractography at thermoplastics is more difficult than in epoxys matrix composites. This is reason is that in thermoplastics the features at the surface morphology are less evident [1].The main fracture features that can be found in plastic composites will be described subsequently:

Fracture Features

DAFF: Directly Attributable Fibre Failure concept is one of the most important features that can be observed in a fracture surface. By this way it is possible to determine the failure propagation direction by a simple observation of the top of the fibers. Determination of the direction of the failure propagation is not the main objective of this work. Thus, not much attention was paid to this aspect [3, 4].

Feather Marks, Scarps and Hackle: Most of the fractographic aspects had their origin at the grain aspects, which, at lower magnification have an aspect of a feather mark. These feather marks indicate the direction of propagation of the failure along one plan. With the increase in the space between the different failure front lines more energy is necessary to regroup the front lines, and this may cause a change in the fracture plane. These changes may create a scarp aspect [1, 3]. If the energy necessary is too big, bigger scarps will be created, and this last are called cusps or hackles [5]. They are relation to the final and rapid growth of the failure. [6]. They also could indicate the strength carried out by the matrix or the level of load submitted to the matrix or the fiber-matrix interface. Hackles are a feature of tough matrix fracture surface [7, 8].

It must be said that many of the thermoplastics features, referred above, were studied for bulk polymers. The presence of rigid fibers in the composites can create shearing forces that can have influence at the fractographic aspects [3].

Environmental: Aeronautical components made of polymeric composites are exposed to a great variety of environmental conditions. Temperature, relative humidity of the air and ultraviolet radiation (UV) are the most dangerous agents present in atmosphere [9].

The environmental effects caused by the temperature and relative humidity of the air can be reversible when the exposition period is of short duration. However, when the exposition time happens in persistent cycles where the changes in moisture-temperatures pair are present, the produced effects can be irreversible. This is caused by the interaction of the water with specific functional groups of polar nature at the polymeric matrix [10, 11, 12]. In that case destructive changes can take place in the fiber-matrix interface. This is due to the degradation of the physicochemical interactions between the matrix and the fiber. In consequence, debonding of the fiber from the matrix can happen, driving to deterioration of the mechanical and thermo-physical properties of the composite [13, 14, 15].

Several authors have accomplished the study of the influence of the humidity content in the mechanical properties of composites materials. These studies show that the increase of the humidity content causes a reduction in tensile, compressive, and flexural strength [13, 16, 17, 18]. In the studies made by Garg [19] it is also verified the harmful effect of humidity and of temperature, that promotes the degradation of the dependent mechanical properties of the matrix and of the interface. The first degradation effect, caused by humidity, is the decrease of the load transfer from matrix to fibers, in compression, deteriorating the resistance of the laminated. That was attributed to the effect of the plasticization of the matrix due to the moisture content, by reducing the T_g (Glass Transition Temperature) and consequently causing degradation of the fiber-matrix interface. The effect of the moisture in the interface promotes the weakness of the chemical adhesions, reducing the interfacial energy and changing the tension state in the interface from compression to tension, causing the debonding of components.

For many matrix materials, the effect of moisture is very similar to the increase of temperature. Collings, Harvey and Dalziel [20] demonstrated experimentally that an increment of temperature of 70°C produces an equivalent effect in the tensile resistance to that of absorption of humidity. Bellenger, Decelle and Huet [21] made another studies confirming the degradation by thermal effect.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The samples were prepared using pre-impregnated laminas of Polyphenylenesulphide (PPS) reinforced with carbon fibers. The fibers were in bi-directional 5 Harness Satin fabrics in $(0,90,45)_s$ ply orientation. The laminas were heated until its melt point and then pressed according to a certain cooling temperature. The samples were cut from these composite laminas with the following dimensions: length \rightarrow 210.0 (\pm 1.5) mm; width \rightarrow 25.0 (\pm 1.5) mm; thickness \rightarrow 1.9 (\pm 0.2) mm.. The tests were conducted at Minho University following the ASTM D 3039 standard [22].

Five samples for each pair moisture/temperature were tested. Tests were carried out in three different temperatures, -55°C , 0°C and 20°C . Conditioning of the samples was according to ASTM D 5229/D 5229M-82 standard [23]. The saturation condition (100%) was obtained inside a conditioning chamber by immersion in hot water (80°C) for 1200 hours. Moisture content was defined by gain of mass. Four conditions of moisture content were chosen: dry, 25%, 50% and 75% of the saturated condition (100%). Tensile tests were carried out in a Dartec servo-hydraulic testing machine with another climatic chamber (test chamber) inside which the samples were tested. The samples were removed from the hot water (inside conditioning chamber) and put inside the testing chamber. Then, after the tests reached the testing temperature they were immediately tested. A specific relative humidity of the air inside the chamber was used to maintain the specimen at the desired moisture condition. The samples were not dried before being tested.

The fractographic study was conducted in a Leica Cambridge S360 Scanning Electronic Microscope at the University of Minho labs. The samples were covered with an ultra fine gold layer to be conductive and then observed at the fracture surface in the SEM.

RESULTS

The tensile strength results are shown in Fig. 1, where can be observed that the amplitude of the tensile strength results is approximately constant for all temperatures. There is a small decrease tendency of the ultimate tensile strength with temperature increase. But it is not clear that there is a tendency of the tensile strength with the moisture content.

Fig. 1: Rupture Tension vs Temperature of the sample

The fractographic analysis revealed some features that could explain this decrease in the ultimate tensile strength. In this study were focused the matrix fracture surface and the fiber-

matrix interface. Small surface areas of DAFF were found in different samples, but were not used to determine the direction of the fracture propagation because this is not the objective of this work. DAFF can be observed in Fig. 2, where the arrows indicate the fracture propagation direction.

Fig. 2: DAFF in a 20°C and 75% moisture absorbed sample. Magnification 3000x.

At -55°C the fracture surface features were almost the same for all moisture contents. At this temperature, the fracture surface showed hackles, scarps and no interfacial failure and bare fibers, for all moisture contents. This can be observed in Fig. 3, Fig. 4, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Fig. 3: Fracture surfaces of -55°C, Dry sample. Magnification 600x.

Fig. 4: Fracture surfaces of -55°C, Dry sample. Magnification 700x.

Fig. 5: Fracture surfaces of -55°C, 75% moisture content sample. Magnification 2000x.

As for -55°C, for 0°C and 20°C there were almost no differences in fracture surface caused by the moisture content. This can be observed in Fig. 7, 8, 9 and 10 for the samples tested at 20°C. Fracture surfaces of samples at 0°C are not shown because they are similar to those at 20°C.

Fig. 6: Fracture surfaces of -55°C, 75% moisture content sample. Magnification 700x.

Fig. 7: Fracture surfaces of 20°C, Dry sample. Magnification 800x.

Contrarily to moisture content that does not show any significant influence on fracture surface morphologies, it is clear a difference between fracture surfaces at different temperatures. While at -55°C the failure surface showed many scarps and hackles, evidencing a more brittle matrix, the surface of the samples tested at 20°C showed a smoother surface, with only few feather patterns, evidencing a more ductile matrix.

Fig. 8: Fracture surfaces of 20°C, Dry sample. Magnification 1500x.

Fig. 9: Fracture surfaces of 20°C, 75% moisture content sample. Magnification 2000x.

Fig. 10: Fracture surfaces of 20°C, 75% moisture content sample. Magnification 700x.

DISCUSSION

The two variables influencing the tensile strength are discussed separately.

Temperature: As expected and based on literature, an increase in temperature causes a decrease in the rupture tension [20, 21]. This was observed mainly for other composite materials, as for epoxy resin matrixes composites. The same rule is applied for thermoplastics matrix composites [3]. This was observed for our thermoplastic matrix composite (see Fig. 1), where for the same saturation condition the tensile decreased with increase in temperature.

Moisture: Many authors found, mainly for epoxy resin matrixes that, moisture has a lower effect than temperature in the rupture strength of the material [13, 16, 17, 18]. They also found that moisture has a tendency to decrease tensile strength. In this study, with a thermoplastic matrix, it is not clear a tendency to increase or decrease tensile strength with moisture content. Some variation in the results exists, but there is no base to state that the increase or decrease in tensile strength is caused by the change in the moisture content. Maybe this small differences and the inexistence of a tendency may be related to the small number of testes made for each condition (5 tests for condition).

Fractography: The fractographic analysis reveals a change in the surface caused by the change at the temperature of the samples tested. For the colder temperatures the fracture surface presents more scarps and hackles. This is attributed to a harder matrix situation [8] or to the velocity of the crack propagation, in this case quickly [5, 6]. This fracture surface had an appearance of a brittle failure. But at higher temperatures the surface looks smoother. This aspect looks like more plastic failure, in a ductile mode [1, 4].

Following this kind of analysis, the colder temperature could “freeze” the thermoplastic matrix causing a more brittle failure instead of that failure that happened at hotter conditions, where the matrix was more ductile, plastic.

However the moisture did not cause detectable changes at the fracture surface. Nothing different was detected that leads to a conclusion that the moisture influences the fracture mode.

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of this work are:

No big differences could be observed both on tensile strength results and on fractographic analyses with a change on moisture content (for the same temperature).

A tendency can be observed on tensile test results with a change in temperature, with a decrease in tensile strength for an increase in temperature.

Fracture surface morphologies are very different for different temperatures, exhibiting a more brittle fracture surface morphology for low temperatures and more ductile fracture morphology for 0°C and 20°C.

Moisture has no influence at the fracture surface.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to say thanks to Ten Cate Advanced Composites, to the University of Minho and to the Brazilian Government, the Brazilian Aeronautical Command and the Aerospace Technical Center (CTA) of Brazil.

This work was supported by the Programme Alþan, European Union Programme of High Level Scholarships for Latin America (n° E03D24712BR).

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